

**“You should all turn to crypto”: the tech magnates’ discourse
around the digital market and why they want to make us think it
is the future.**

Anna Valenti

Student number: 13530232

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Michael Stevenson

Introduction

The market is changing, and its future is digital. Since Bitcoin entered the scene in 2009, cryptocurrencies have become the new gold, and people are enthusiastic about that. The increasing popularity of crypto is dramatically impacting the way we think of money: how to earn it, save it, and how it should be perceived and traded. However, this interest in the crypto market, together with diffused utopian views about its future, is also the result of the widespread debate around the topic among digital intermediaries. Public utterances of influential social figures have a huge impact on the fluctuation of cryptocurrencies. Their discourse shapes the market, and their statements echo old imaginaries about digital gold that still resonate today. The result is a strong relationship between reputation and value of cryptocurrencies, which seem to be co-dependent. Their objective may seem unclear; however, the ideals that permeate their discourse suggest the intention to undermine the foundations of the common market.

The aim of this study is to dismantle the public claims around cryptocurrencies of digital intermediaries (e.g., Elon Musk) to obtain a clearer understanding of their meaning and goal. This type of discourse varies widely across platforms and contexts, and this research focuses on finding a common ground that can explain the ideas and perspectives behind it. I suggest that these kinds of public utterances while recalling aspects of both the digital metallist and the infrastructural mutualist imaginaries, and chaining the concept of value market to that of reputation, propose the embracement of the crypto market in opposition to state power to favor new digital elites.

Background

The words of today's tech magnates suggest how their vision around cryptocurrencies is still extremely tied to the first imaginaries originated in the debate. Digging into the past of cryptocurrencies is therefore essential to understanding the future (Swartz 2018, 624). The ideals and dreams of the first Bitcoin enthusiasts first led to a fundamental division between "two analytically distinct techno-economic imaginaries" (Swartz 2018, 630): digital metallism and infrastructural mutualism. The former is "firmly rooted in an idealized vision of the market" (Swartz 2018, 631), and suggests the idea of a market untied to state policy, "without anyone to regulate" (Karlstrøm 2014, 2). This imaginary has its roots in the crypto-anarchism ideology of the first years of Bitcoin, which is still particularly resonant today. The crypto-anarchists believed that cryptocurrencies and their technology – the blockchain – could ensure freedom, of speech and of the market (Swartz 2018, 627), and they believed in "no laws except those that can be described by math and enforced by code" (Narayanan 2013, 76). This strong faith in the market and in the technology that comes with cryptocurrencies is still one of the key elements of the analyzed debate. Infrastructural mutualism, on the other hand, stresses on the privacy of transactions and "a cooperativist vision of a money

technology and therefore society” (Swartz 2018, 632). As a consequence, these two imaginaries appear profoundly different, and their tensions, Swartz says, “insurmountable” (2018, 634). This study, however, shows how such distinct views of the market are both strongly embedded in current discourses around cryptocurrencies.

The debate around Bitcoin and Blockchain does not spark spontaneously but is often originated from and carried by digital intermediaries. By digital intermediaries, I refer to the definition given by Pecourt Garcia and Rius-Ulldemolins (2018), namely a “variety of agents” (company, organizations, prominent figures) who “conform a range of positions ... but share common elements in their understanding of digital culture, such as their understanding of technology’s effect on social change” (Pecourt Garcia and Rius-Ulldemolins 2018, 74). These intermediaries’ discourse has a huge impact on society and its perspective on technology since they are said to be the “most visible casualties of digital utopianism’s conception of culture” (Pecourt Garcia and Rius-Ulldemolins 2018, 75). This “profound faith in the emancipatory potential of the new information technologies” (Barbrook and Cameron 1996, 12) has been defined as “Californian ideology” in the 1990s, but it is still alive and vibrating today: the discourse of tech magnates is now more than ever steeped of an untouched trust in technology and its future potential. The current hegemony of this contradictory combination of technological determinism and libertarian individualism has led to an inevitable dependence on the new digital elite of tech magnates, to which Barbrook and Cameron refer as “virtual class” (1996, 15). More specifically, with this term they allude to well-paid, privileged hi-tech artisans (e.g., computer scientists, engineers, communication specialists), who own great autonomy in their job and are fundamental for their creative design of digital products and software (Barbrook and Cameron 1996).

This paper addresses the two case studies of Elon Musk and the Meta company. Previous research has already analyzed their discourse, but it often lacks an interpretative approach, together with a wider consideration of the intertextuality. Huynh (2022) conducted a content analysis of Elon Musk’s tweets, establishing the causal relationship between the CEO’s words and changes in the cryptocurrencies’ charts. The survey carried out by Ynag et al. (2022) studied the fusion of AI technologies and blockchain within the metaverse. This study not only provides a clear explanation of the functioning of the metaverse economy but also gives an insight into how digital currency represents the main media for transactions in the metaverse and how the blockchain “is widely believed as one of the fundamental infrastructures of metaverse” (Ynag et al. 2022, 7). These works, however, do not address the imaginaries, promises, and objectives that lay behind the debate around cryptocurrencies. The depiction of the technology provided by tech magnates is often overlooked by research, that focuses more on the direct correlation of their statements with value in the market. The

aim of this paper is to lay out a complete analysis of the ideologies and ambitions implied in these claims, in particular through the comparison of different types of discourse.

Method

The analysis conducted in this paper provides a particular perspective on the debate. For this study, I focused on some of Elon Musk's tweets about DogeCoin, on the "Founders' Letter" by Mark Zuckerberg, published on the Meta website (2022), and on the web page of the new Meta's digital wallet app, Novi. I decided to focus on these sources since their variety provides a broader overview of the discourse around cryptocurrencies. Their format and audience are profoundly different, but my analysis highlights the interconnections between them and their ultimate aim. The tweets are responsible for important fluctuations of cryptocurrency's value: they were selected for their apparently insignificant relevance to the market, which actually hides how the aforementioned imaginaries subtly perpetuate themselves on social media platforms. Afterward, Meta's utopian views on the future favored an increasing trust in the employment of cryptocurrencies. In Mark Zuckerberg's claims about the future, cryptocurrencies are not constantly mentioned, but always silently included. The two types of discourses analyzed have, therefore, a fundamental role in the changes in market conditions and illustrate two different approaches to them.

The analysis that I conducted is primarily textual: I picked apart the components of the discourse of these intermediaries, to understand their significance. I studied how these discourses fit in different media environments, with an attention to their different formats. The recurrent identified topics have been compared with the attempt to investigate how they interlinked with each other in a complex patchwork. Accordingly, my findings consist of the three main ideas that permeate their discourse and that bring together the visions of the intermediaries under analysis.

Analysis

The public discourse of Elon Musk and Meta aims at providing their audience with a specific view of the crypto market and its future potential. These digital intermediaries are interested not only in the technology itself represented by cryptocurrencies but also in the imaginaries this technology bears with it. The three main claims that can be retrieved from their discourses are that: 1) cryptocurrencies represent the possibility of a free market, in which institutions have no choice in the matter, 2) working together to implement the crypto market means that a greater profit can be obtained from it, 3) trusting these people and organizations is the best choice to aim at a better future.

Money is not a state affair

Relying on the common market is no more an option for the digital elites. In 2021 Elon Musk tweeted: “No highs, no lows, only Doge” (2021). Even though this statement could be interpreted as an unpretentious joke, it represents much more than that: it is a crypto-anarchist claim masked by humor. Laughing at the hilarious and wild essence of the Doge crypto coin is nothing but a further detachment from the “boring” nature of the common market, regularly controlled by traditional institutions. Meta is also aiming for a better – and different – future. Its metaverse will be built on the principles of “open standards and interoperability” (Zuckerberg 2021). The company directly associates these principles with the emergent crypto market, stating that this openness will require “supporting crypto and NFT projects in the community” (Zuckerberg 2021). On the web page that promotes the digital wallet Novi, the company enlists all the benefits of using digital currencies as a payment method. For instance, they claim how digital currencies “remove steps and fees” (Novi 2022). This assertion subtly suggests that cryptocurrencies are cheaper and easier to use, rather than the long and expensive bureaucratic processes, which are a result of state regulation.

This aspiration to a free market, that detaches from the state’s authority, clearly recalls the idealized perspective of digital metallists (Swartz 2018). An economy with “open standards” (Zuckerberg 2021) does not contemplate the strict government policies; moreover, its openness and anonymous nature that shrinks regulation “only seems to add to its allure” (Karlstrøm 2014, 2). The utopian image given by Meta of a simple system whose worth is unaffected by taxation still draws on the digital metallist theory that “the only truly sound money is one ... which derives its intrinsic value from the market” (Swartz 2018, 630). Differently, its value is subject to manipulation from authorities: since cryptocurrencies are not governed by policies and fees, they appear as a revolutionary factor in the system, “untethered from fallible institutions” (Swartz 2018, 630).

Together we can do better (and earn more)

In another tweet from 2021, Elon Musk said: “DogeCoin is the people’s crypto” (2021). The perspective provided on cryptocurrencies by digital intermediaries is that of a system which everyone could contribute to while protecting their interests and privacy. Meta shares similar objectives, as the Founder’s letter recalls: “Privacy and safety need to be built into the metaverse from day one” (Zuckerberg 2021). This statement suggests an infrastructural mutualist view on money, in which privacy is prioritized (Swartz 2018). The only way to protect it is therefore to adopt a payment system that assures anonymity: thus, cryptocurrencies. Additionally, in the video explaining why Novi is a wallet for digital currencies, the company declares that the blockchain technology is safer than the “usual” way of exchanging money: it is “built on a trusted network, making transactions instant and automated” (Novi 2022).

This infrastructural mutualist perspective that cryptocurrencies and their blockchain technology could ensure privacy and security is strongly highlighted in the analyzed discourses. This approach dates to the crypto-anarchist community, which promoted anonymity (Karlstrøm 2014). The idea that privacy and anonymity mean safety also goes back to the digital utopistic idea of the first Bitcoin enthusiasts, who “posit that in a world dominated by electronic modes of communication, the possibilities for anonymity means that the threat of violence diminishes” (Karlstrøm 2014, 7). The use of these intermediaries is suggesting is that of “crypto-for-privacy” (Narayanan 2013, 75), which often pursues social and political interests (Narayanan 2013).

Trust us, not the system

The aim of these actors’ discourses is that of building a social image that people can trust. The result is the interconnection between value in the market and reputation in the social arena. Another tweet by Elon Musk cites “Ur welcome” (2021), with an attached meme representing Rafiki, the monkey from the Disney animated feature film “The Lion King” (Allers and Minkoff 1994), holding the young lion Simba in his hands. In the image, the face of Musk is photoshopped on Rafiki’s, while the dog logo of the DogeCoin is superimposed on Simba’s body. Through this fun representation, Musk depicts himself as a leader, someone to trust in the transition to digital currencies. Meta adopts the same persuasive strategy, guarantying that “the metaverse will reach a billion people, host hundreds of billions of dollars of digital commerce, and support jobs for millions of creators and developers” (Zuckerberg 2021). Meta wants to show that its claims are well supported, and it does that by depicting its project as the brightest future possible.

The attitudes of tech magnates towards the future are definitely optimistic and they adhere to the promise embedded in the Californian ideology once described by Barbrook and Cameron (1996): “In the digital utopia, everybody will be both hip and rich” (1996, 12). The promise that technology will improve our lives is stronger than ever in today’s debate around cryptocurrencies. The role that digital intermediaries will play in it is already defined by themselves: they are the leaders, and they have all the tools and power to carry out their purpose. The strategy adopted by these intermediaries is that of a “discursive construction of trust” (Woodall and Ringel 2020, 200), aiming at replacing trust in the government and state policies with a trust in the blockchain and the crypto free market (Woodall and Ringel 2020, 2205). Trust, which is the result of “integrity, authenticity and reliability” (2020, 2212), is a key element for the ideals and projects depicted by digital intermediaries. This increasing faith in their leadership ties their reputation to the value of cryptocurrencies in the market since their statements are often responsible for its fluctuation (Huynh 2022). Indeed, the popularity of a cryptocurrency is often closely tied to the popularity of “traders, miners, wallets and exchanges” (Rehman et al. 2020, 1204).

Discussion: a new (dis)order?

All the excitement and enthusiasm communicated through the tech magnates' words previously analyzed are all funneled towards a precise objective: making cryptocurrencies the center of gravity of the economy of the future. However, I argue that this particular purpose hides a bigger aspiration: the shift of authority from the government to the new digital elites. Since "Bitcoin represents some challenges to the status quo" (Karlstrøm 2014, 2), the introduction of an alternative market to the common one, in which there are no taxations nor policies, that is not regulated nor controlled by anyone, is the first step to subvert the current order. The optimistic trust in blockchain technology for a better future still bears the crypto-anarchist promise for an "anarcho-capitalist market system" (May 1994). For the actors involved, crypto technology is the key to a "truly free market society" (Swartz 2018, 627).

However, the free market these intermediaries are aiming to is not one in which there is no external intervention, but one that is still linked to virtual and non-virtual institutions (Karlstrøm 2014). Actually, cryptocurrencies are still a threat to the reigning order, but they are also still profoundly rooted in material and institutional matters (Karlstrøm 2014). Nevertheless, new digital elites are trying to shift the focal point in the digital market environment. They sidestep from the current governmental orders, seeing no "positive connection between democracy and money" (Brockmann et al. 2021). However, even though their statements communicate that they feel to have a mission, their attitude is contradictory (Brockmann et al. 2021). Their free view of the market, with the aim to gain financial success, does not match with the current democratic regime; they are claiming the right to tell the future, and they are doing that to advantage themselves (Murtola 2018).

Even though supporting the blockchain technology and virtual economy, Musk notably declared that Tesla would not accept any more purchases made using Bitcoin (Musk 2021). He stated that the decision was made due to concern about the environmental cost of Bitcoin mining that uses coal, which is the fuel with the most impactful emissions (Musk 2021). Musk affirms again that "cryptocurrency is a good idea on many levels" (2021), but that its future cannot involve this huge negative effect on the environment (Musk 2021). The employment of such a problematic currency, for a company that is known for its "green" technology, would have radically affected their reputation. However, in following tweets, Elon Musk still expresses his support towards blockchain and digital currencies. This event shows how tech magnates' adherence to blockchain's ideologies is often followed by the transformation of these imaginaries for their benefits and business' needs.

The future they are depicting is one not governed by laws and politics, but by capital (Murtola 2018). However, this possible scenario would only increase plutocracy, making the wealthy wealthier and more powerful (Murtola 2018). Therefore, while criticizing the current capitalistic

present, the new digital elites are working not to transform it, as they want their audience to believe, but to adjust it to create a future “in their own image” (Murtola 2018, 8).

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to reframe the discourse of influential tech intermediaries around cryptocurrencies to unscramble its meaning and obtain a clearer understanding of the imaginaries and perspectives it bears with it. The textual analysis that was conducted in this study dismantled the claims made by Elon Musk and Mark Zuckerberg and showed how the current debate on the digital market still echoes old imaginaries on digital gold (i.e., infrastructural mutualism and digital metallism). Moreover, a closer look at the better place these actors are trying to turn the world into (Gates 2021) revealed how the real intention that lays behind their statements is actually that of subverting the current status quo, so as to gain a bigger profit in the future they are portraying to their audiences. This investigation has analyzed and compared the recurrent features of the selected claims. It highlighted how the perspective of a free market that regulates itself is still resonant, together with a strong concern around privacy and safety. My analysis also showed how the selected words used by the magnates of interest strive to construct trust through discourse (Woodall and Ringel 2020) and to benefit from it. I also looked at how the concept of value has changed, and how it is now strongly tied to reputation. Finally, this study’s purpose was to contribute to the decoding of the discourse of these actors, investigating how messages of different authors and formats could interlink with each other through recurrent topics and shared perspectives. Future research could further study how the discourse changes across years and platforms, through the analysis of a larger number of actors involved. Moreover, one could also dig deeper into the imaginaries embedded in the debate, looking not only at past references but also at present and future perspectives on money, widening the field of observation.

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Reflection on changes

The changes that have been apported to the paper regard mainly the method and the analysis sections. I cut off the Amazon's case study to focus on the case studies of Elon Musk and the Meta company. I interpreted differently, as the feedback suggested, one of the tweets analyzed, and I reframed part of the analysis of the Meta's company discourse. Indeed, I added the primary source of the Novi's website to gain further insight into the company's perspective on the digital market. Moreover, I added the concept of "the virtual class" to my theoretical framework. I fixed the formatting of the paper, making it more consistent. I also moved one of the concepts of my theoretical framework, the "discursive construction of trust", into the analysis, where it was more appropriate since it resulted as a finding. I restated some argumentations that were not very clear, and I improved the transitions between some of the paragraphs. I also made my analysis more supported by adding some more findings to it.